

议程 Programme

Arches: an architectural/structural never-ending story

第一周 Week 1

9月17日 星期一 Monday 17th September
 8:30-12:00 学生登记与暑期班介绍
 Enrollment and Introduction
 14:00-17:30 福州大学与实验室介绍
 Introduction to FZU and Labs
 9月18日 星期二 Tuesday 18th September
 8:30-12:00 开展课题活动 Start of Project Activities
 14:00-17:30 陈述结构形态的方法
 Presentation on Methodology in Structural Morphology
 9月19日 星期三 Wednesday 19th September
 8:30-12:00 结构优化原则
 Principles of Structural Optimization
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work

9月20-21日 星期四-星期五 Tuesday-Friday 20th-21st September
 参观学习 (例如: 土楼)
 Guided Site learning (eg. 土楼 Tulou)

9月22日 星期六 Saturday 22nd September
 8:30-12:00 天桥结构优化
 Structural Optimization in Footbridges
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 9月23日 星期天 Sunday 23rd September
 8:30-12:00 OCP结构优化的方法和软件
 Approaches and Software for Structural Optimization-OCP
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work

第二周 Week 2

9月24日 星期一 Monday 24th September
 中秋节 The mid-Autumn Festival
 9月25日 星期二 Tuesday 25th September
 8:30-12:00 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 9月26日 星期三 Wednesday 26th September
 8:30-12:00 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 9月27日 星期四 Thursday 27th September
 8:30-12:00 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 14:00-17:30 课堂作业 Classroom Work
 9月28日 星期五 Friday 28th September
 8:30-12:00 项目汇报和成果准备
 Project -presentation and results preparation
 14:00-17:30 项目汇报和成果准备
 Project -presentation and results preparation
 9月29日 星期六 Saturday 28th September
 8:30-12:00 最终成果展示、颁奖与闭幕典礼
 Final Presentation of Projects
 Awarding and Closing Ceremony

组织与学术委员会

Organizing and Scientific Committee

Fuzhou University		
B. Briseghella	G. C. Marano	Z. S. Lin
J.G. Wei	B.C. Chen	X. Wu
C.B. Hu	W.D. Zhuo	W. Lu
T. Zhang	L.B. Chen	C. Zhao
T. Deng	J.Q. Xue	
Roma Tre University		
C. Nuti	S. Santini	D. Lavorato
A. Bergami	F. Sabetta	G. Fiorentino
F. Paolacci		
National Technical University		
N. Lagaros		
Polytechnic University of Bari		
R. Greco	F. Trentadue	F. Defilippis
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia		
M. A. Tarantino	L. Lanzoni	
University of Chieti-Pescara		
I. Vanzi	E. Spacone	G. Brando
University of Cagliari		University of L'Aquila
L. Fenu	A. Gregori	

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福州大学土木工程学院与建筑学院

College of Civil Engineering - Fuzhou University

以及 and with the support of

College of Architecture - Fuzhou University

福州大学-罗马第三大学中意交流中心

Fuzhou- Roma Tre Sino-Italian Center

以及 and

国立雅典理工大学

National Technical University of Athens

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第三届“结构形态”夏令营

SSSM18

Third International

Summer School

“Structural Morphology”

福州, 2018年09月17-29号

Fuzhou, September 17-29, 2018

摘要 Abstract

One of the deepest and central theme in design is the relationship between geometry and structures. How geometrical shapes influence forces' flow into elements is a basic point to better understand and design structures.

The so-called "optimal" geometrical shape has a strong influence on structure definition, as the coupling between form and forces, usually called structural morphology, is a key point for success to solve challenging structural problems, both using conventional materials or innovative shapes and technologies.

This School is focused on a practical approach to the coupling between form and forces in design, with emphasis on harmonizing the architectural and engineering vision.

设计中最深刻、最核心的主题之一是几何与结构的关系。几何图形如何影响力的流动是一个基本点，以更好地理解 and 设计结构。

所谓“最优”的几何形状对结构定义有强大的影响力，形与力之间的耦合，通常称为结构形态，是成功解决结构问题的一个关键点，无论是使用传统材料还是使用创新的形状和技术。

这次活动的重点是找到一个实用的方法，在设计中形成形式和力之间的耦合，强调达成工程和建筑形象之间的和协。

主题介绍 Contents

The Summer School starting point is the reinterpretation of the main consolidated "forms" and the relationships between the spatial configurations and structures. Particular importance will be given to the possible morphological - structural "forms" (through geometric, static and materials logics), rethought in order to obtain new design and production methods.

Footbridges will be used as case study, analysing both the architectural applications and structural solutions for a number of real configurations.

Computer supports for the geometrical and analytical aspects of structural design are a specific tool that will be used by students to develop the case studies.

暑期班从对主要整合“形式”重新解读出发，探讨空间形态与结构的关系。尤其重视可能的形态结构的“形式”（通过几何、静态和材料的逻辑），反思以获得新的设计和制造方法。

以人行桥作为研究案例，从建筑应用和结构方案来分析大量实际的布局。

计算机支持的结构设计方面的几何和分析作为一个特别的工具，将用于学生发展自己的研究案例。

比赛 Contest

The summer school will be based on a group design approach and specific lessons done by expert in different fields involved in structural morphology.

Working groups will be organised in teams composed by students from different countries, both with engineering and architecture backgrounds, to guarantee a complete contamination between form and structure.

Each group will produce a final project, comprehensive of drawings, animation, 3D rendering and real scale models. As final result, solution developed to properly satisfy both architectural aspects and structural safety requirements will be presented to a public evaluation committee.

暑期班将基于小组设计的方法，由与结构形态相关的不同领域专家授课。

小组将由中国和国外学生构成，兼有工程和建筑背景，以达成满足形式和结构的充分交流。

每个小组将产生一个最终的方案，以详细的图纸，动画，三维透视图和实体模型表达。作为最终的结果，应适当地满足建筑方面和结构安全的要求，提交给公共评估委员会。

